

SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF BISMALLEIMIDE BASED THERMOSET TRIPLE-SHAPE POLYMERIC SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Shape memory polymers (SMPs) as a type of smart materials have achieved remarkable advances in recent years. Thermoset SMPs with potential applications in aerospace, textiles and household products have attracted great interests of researchers for its unique properties. In order to further enhance and broaden the applications of SMPs, more unprecedented functions are necessary for the applications above, especially for aerospace. In this paper, the synthesis and characterization of triple-shape shape memory polymers (TSMPs) that, unlike traditional shape memory polymers, are capable of fixing two temporary shapes and recovering sequentially from the first temporary shape (shape 1) to the second temporary shape (shape 2), and eventually to the permanent shape (shape 3) upon heating, are reported. For thermoset polymers, ordinarily, such complexity in physical behaviour is achieved through proper addition of thermoplastic polymers or comparable complexity in material structure. Seeking to synthesize thermoset polymers with intrinsic triple-shape shape memory behaviour, we introduce here a method that exploit the broad glass transition temperature range of polymer. Thus, to yield the requisite combination of chemical structure and composition, new thermosetting bismaleimide (BMI) based shape memory polymers were synthesized and characterized. We show that all synthetic products exhibited broad transition temperature range needed for triple shape behaviour. The glass transition temperature and shape memory properties are varied using a diisocyanate resin creating a urea crosslinking moiety between the linear chains. Characterization of the triple shape behaviour revealed an ability of all samples to fix two separate deformations independently, one at the beginning of the glass transition process and a second one at the end of the glass transition process, and recover both programmed shapes separately upon heating. Given the simplicity of fabrication, we envision application as multi-shape coatings, adhesives, and films.

1 INTRODUCTION

Shape memory polymers (SMPs) are a class of materials which have the ability of being fixed into a temporary shape and then recovering to their initial shape while exposed to an external stimulus [1,2] such as heat [3], light [4], electric or magnetic fields [5], solvent [6], pH value [7] and even enzyme [8]. By realizing the connection between the chemical structure and crucial properties, thermosetting SMPs have a permanent shape as a result of a crosslinking network. Their shape can be changed to a temporary shape by external force when the materials are heated above a critical transition temperature and fixed by freezing polymer chains at a temperature lower than the SMPs transition temperature [9]. The shape recovery which resulted from polymer chain segments relaxation could be observed during reheating process of SMPs under stress-free condition. While SMPs have such a unique capability as polymer matrix of shape memory materials, applications in various areas such as biomedical devices [10], sensors [11], smart textiles [12] and deployable space structures [13] have been reported.

In recent years, there are a large number of SMPs with new properties emerging with a rapid development of their applications. The conventional shape memory polymers only can have a dual shape memory effect. For extending the range of applications, multiple shape memory polymers which

have the capability of memorizing three or more shapes during the shape changing and recovery process have been investigated. Most current researches focus on the thermoplastic polymeric systems [14,15]. However, for thermosetting polymers, the attentions being paid to multiple shape memory effect are inadequate. Mather et al. blended epoxy and poly (ϵ -caprolactone) as a simple route of producing a triple shape memory composite [16]. This method utilized polymerization induced phase separation to yield the requisite combination of microstructure and composition. Xie et al. reported a different method based on a polymer bilayer structure consisting of thermosetting epoxy with two different glass transition temperatures [17]. Via changing the ratio of thickness of the two layers, the shape memory properties could be tuned easily. However, these two physical approaches both have negative influences on the properties of thermosetting SMPs. In order to overcome this drawback, it is necessary to fabricate thermosetting polymer with intrinsic multiple shape memory effect.

In this paper, we describe the synthesis of bismaleimide (BMI) based triple-shape memory polymers, revealing that the broad glass transition temperature range of thermoset polymer contribute to triple shape memory behavior. Their thermal and mechanical properties affected by the crosslink density are discussed in detail. The triple shape memory effects caused by complex covalent crosslinks are characterized in both tensile tests and bending tests, which result in an excellent potential for aerospace applications.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The 4, 4'-bismaleimidodiphenylmethane (BDM) and 2,2'-bis (4-cyanatophenyl) propane were purchased from Tokyo Chemical Industry CO., LTD. The Jeffamine D-400 (poly (oxy (methyl-1, 2-ethanediyl)), alpha-(2-aminoethylenthy)l) omega-(2-aminomethylethoxy), (JA-400)) was purchased from Aladdin. The chemical structures were depicted in Fig.1. All chemicals were used as received without further purification.

Figure 1: Structures of (a) 4,4'-Bismaleimidodiphenylmethane (BDM), (b) Jeffamine D-400 (JA-400), and (c) 2,2'-bis (4-cyanatophenyl) propane.

2.2 Polymer synthesis

The BDM was reacted with JA-400 to build the linear backbone of the molecular structure by following a reported method [18]. The progress of the reaction was carried out in the solvent of tetrahydrofuran (THF) at the temperature of 338K for 24h under an argon atmosphere. Then the weighed 2,2-bis (4-cyanatophenyl) propane was added to the solution with stirring. The resulting mixture was poured to the mold after removing any particles and dried over for 24h at room temperature. The resulting rubbery polymeric system was thermally cured at 200°C. Eventually, the shape memory polymer sheets were fabricated.

Table 1: Details of SMP synthesis.

Sample No.	0	50	100	150	200
Mole fraction of BDM/JA-400/BACE	1/1/0	1/1/0.25	1/1/0.5	1/1/0.75	1/1/1

2.3 Methods

For demonstrating the crosslinking density of BMI based SMPs, here we use swelling tests to evaluate the growing trend. The weighed samples were immersed in four different solvents for about 24 h. Then the samples were taken out of the solvents and cleared up the residual solvents on surface. By measuring the mass increase of samples, we could qualitatively compare the crosslinking density of samples. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC, METTLER TOLEDO DSC1) measurements were used to characterize the change in the thermal properties of the polymers from 25 °C to 200 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. The glass transition temperature (T_g) values were obtained as the inflection temperatures in the DSC curves. The thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was obtained by a Mettler-Toledo thermal analysis instrument. The data was collected at a heating rate of 10°C/min with the protective atmosphere of N₂.

The triple shape memory behaviors in this study were also characterized by using a visual bending test. Each rectangular sample was prepared at the size of 70×5×1 mm³ and first heated to a higher temperature over its T_g for 5 min. Then one side of strip was quickly folded on one end at this time, and the sample was moved into a lower temperature oven with external constraint to fix the first temporary shape. After that, the second temporary shape was obtained by external force on the other end of each strip and fixed at room temperature. When the sample was heated to the deformation temperature again, triple shape recovery could be observed on each side respectively.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Polymer swell testing

Swell tests were conducted on each of the four generated thermosetting SMP materials to gage crosslink densities. A solvent base was selected covering a broad polarity index, water being the most polar (9.0), methanol (5.1), THF (4.0), and toluene being the least polar (2.4). Each sample was exposed for 24 h. From the graph illustrated in Figure 2, comparative crosslink densities can be inferred for the SMPs. As a trend, the greater the amount of BACE used during synthesis, a greater chemical crosslinking density was achieved resulting in a decrease in swelling by mass increase. The least amount of activity is seen in the tests involving water and toluene. In water and toluene, a very small increase in mass is observed across all materials. The mass increases of all samples fluctuated below 10%. In contrast, the materials showed the greatest interactions with methanol and THF. The lesser crosslink density material (TSMP50) swelled nearly twice the amount of the materials with the greatest crosslink densities (TSMP200). Thus we can see that the crosslinking density of samples increases with the amount of BACE we used.

Figure 2: BMI based TSMPs swell test results.

3.2 Differential scanning calorimetry analysis

The typical DSC curves of our TSMPs are shown in Figure 3. The baseline sample No. 0 is also included in the figure as “REF” for comparison purposes. The glass transition of crosslinked samples could be observed from their DSC curves. T_g of the samples were 90°C, 100°C, 110°C and 115°C for TSMP50, TSMP100, TSMP150 and TSMP200, respectively. The T_g was increased by 25°C compared TSMP50 with TSMP200. This could be attributed to the increasing crosslinking density of crosslinked samples. The test results are consistent with swelling test. In the molecular level, the T_g increase could be explained by the weakening activity of amorphous chain segment. Furthermore, there are no other changes could be observed from these curves during the heating process. It demonstrates that the crosslinking reaction is complete.

Figure 3: DSC heating scans of TSMPs

3.3 Thermogravimetric analysis

TGA in nitrogen is used to investigate the thermal stability of BMI based TSMPs from 25°C to 600°C. The overall comparison of the TGA curves and the derivative of the weights are shown in Figure 4. The baseline sample No. 0 is also included in the figure as “REF” for comparison purposes. The average temperatures at which 5% weight loss is observed are 291.5°C, 270.5°C, 224.8°C, and 225.7°C for synthesized TSMP50, TSMP100, TSMP150 and TSMP200, respectively. TSMP150 and TSMP200 show early thermal instabilities in both curves. This can possibly be attributed to a transport-limited reaction between secondary amines leading to species with premature thermal breakdown. The average char residue value of the TSMPs at 600°C is 12.22%, 8.81%, 6.79%, and 6.00%. The increase of crosslinking density has little adverse effect on thermo stability of TSMPs. Major chemical decomposition can be seen by examining the derivative of the weight curves, which begin at about 400°C. In general, it indicates that the TSMPs remained thermally stable at their service temperatures.

Figure 4: TGA analysis results of BMI based TSMPs

3.4 Triple-shape memory behaviors of BMI based TSMPs

Sample TSMP150 is chosen to characterize the triple shape memory behavior due to its broad T_g range showing in DSC curves (Figure 3). DMA test under force control mode was used to analyze the triple shape memory behavior quantitatively. To make the triple shape memory effect more obviously, the temperatures at the beginning and the end of glass transition were employed as the deformed temperature. Figure 5a presents the stress–strain–temperature curve of TSMP150. Triple shape memory behaviour was achieved by a “two-step” method. At first, the sample is stretched to 8% strain at 160 °C, and cooled to 80 °C to fix temporary shape “S1” under 0.6 N external force. After that the force was decreased to 0.001 N and the sample was kept for 5 mins. Then, the sample was further stretched to 10% strain at 80 °C and fixed at 25 °C to obtain another temporary shape “S2” with the constant force of 3N. At last, the force was released and the sample was reheated. When the temperature reached 80 °C, the temporary shape “S1” was obtained again. Further heated to 160 °C, the shape would change toward the original state “S0”. The equations to calculate shape fixed ratio (R_f) and shape recovery ratio (R_r) are as follows:

$$R_f(x \rightarrow y) = \frac{\varepsilon_y - \varepsilon_x}{\varepsilon_{y, load} - \varepsilon_x} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

$$R_r(x \rightarrow y) = \frac{\varepsilon_x - \varepsilon_{y, rec}}{\varepsilon_x - \varepsilon_y} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

where x and y stand for different shapes of the sample in a shape memory cycle; “load” and “rec” represent the strain before unloading and the strain after recovery, respectively. R_f (S0-S1) and R_f (S1-S2) are up to 99% and 96%, respectively. Meanwhile, R_f (S2-S1) and R_f (S1-S0) could reach 92% and 99%, respectively. The high R_f and R_r indicate TSMP150 shows an excellent triple shape memory behavior.

Figure 5b exhibits the visual demonstration of the triple shape memory behavior via a bending-recovery test. It is clear that TSMP150 could successfully memorize two temporary shapes.

Figure 5: Triple-shape memory process of TSMP150

4 CONCLUSIONS

A series of BMI based triple shape memory polymers were successfully synthesized by using a bisphenol-A cyanate ester as modifier to increase complexity of amorphous networks which contributed to the broad range of glass transition temperature. Swelling test indicated that the amorphous polymer networks with different crosslinking density were formed. The DSC curves indicated the T_g increases with the increasing crosslinking density. The thermal stability of the TSMPs was also influenced by the crosslink density. By using two distinct deformation temperatures within the range of glass transition, triple shape memory behavior could be achieved from all samples, where two shapes were independently recovered in response to heat stimulus. The research about the polymers which are able to memorize each temporary shape after a more complex deformation process need to deepen more in the future.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Behl, M. and A. Lendlein (2007). "Shape-memory polymers." *Materials Today* 10(4): 20-28.
- [2] Leng, J., et al. (2011). "Shape-memory polymers and their composites: Stimulus methods and applications." *Progress in Materials Science* 56(7): 1077-1135.
- [3] Lendlein, A. and S. Kelch (2002). "Shape-Memory Polymers." *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 41(12): 2034-2057.
- [4] Lendlein, A., et al. (2005). "Light-induced shape-memory polymers." *Nature* 434(7035): 879-882.
- [5] Sahoo, N. G., et al. (2010). "Polymer nanocomposites based on functionalized carbon nanotubes." *Progress in Polymer Science* 35(7): 837-867.
- [6] Lv, H., et al. (2008). "Shape-Memory Polymer in Response to Solution." *Advanced Engineering Materials* 10(6): 592-595.
- [7] Han, X. J., et al. (2012). "pH-Induced Shape-Memory Polymers." *Macromolecular Rapid Communications* 33(12): 1055-1060.
- [8] Roy, D., et al. (2010). "Future perspectives and recent advances in stimuli-responsive materials." *Progress in Polymer Science* 35(1-2): 278-301.
- [9] Liu, C., et al. (2007). "Review of progress in shape-memory polymers." *Journal of Materials Chemistry* 17(16): 1543-1558.
- [10] Serrano, M. C., et al. (2011). "Novel Biodegradable Shape-Memory Elastomers with Drug-Releasing Capabilities." *Advanced Materials* 23(19): 2211-2215.
- [11] Kunzelman, J., et al. (2008). "Shape memory polymers with built-in threshold temperature sensors." *Journal of Materials Chemistry* 18(10): 1082-1086.
- [12] Hu, J. and S. Chen (2010). "A review of actively moving polymers in textile applications." *Journal of Materials Chemistry* 20(17): 3346-3355.

- [13] Lan, X., et al. (2009). "Fiber reinforced shape-memory polymer composite and its application in a deployable hinge." *Smart Materials and Structures* 18(2): 024002.
- [14] Xie, T. (2010). "Tunable polymer multi-shape memory effect." *Nature* 464(7286): 267-270.
- [15] Dolog, R. and R. A. Weiss (2013). "Shape Memory Behavior of a Polyethylene-Based Carboxylate Ionomer." *Macromolecules* 46(19): 7845-7852.
- [16] Torbati, A. H., et al. (2014). "Properties of triple shape memory composites prepared via polymerization-induced phase separation." *Soft Matter* 10(17): 3112-3121.
- [17] Xie, T., et al. (2009). "Revealing Triple-Shape Memory Effect by Polymer Bilayers." *Macromolecular Rapid Communications* 30(21): 1823-1827.
- [18] Shen, Z. W., et al. (1998). "Synthesis and characterization of leather impregnated with bismaleimide (BMI) - Jeffamine (R) resins." *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* 69(5): 1019-1027.